

Modulating activity and selectivity of aqueous phase furfuryl alcohol hydrogenation by tuning supported Pt on W-Zr Mixed oxides

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ABSTRACT

This work investigated a mixed W_xZr_y oxide supported-platinum catalyst for the selective synthesis of cyclopentanone (CPO) from furfuryl alcohol (FOL). The tuning effect of different W and Zr molar ratio with varying Pt loadings at various operating temperatures and P_{H₂} were explored under aqueous phase conditions in a flow-through configuration. Different WO_x domain and Pt⁰ crystallite sizes were obtained as a function of Zr content in the supports. These modulations exhibited distinct selectivities towards the reaction intermediates. Furthermore, water was found to complement as a source of homogeneous catalysis for FOL rearrangement at high temperatures. Minimal hydrogenation intermediates were detected using only W_xZr_y supports. While the presence of Pt does enhance hydrogenation activity, it also resulted in reduction of WO_x domains necessary for reaction steps beyond FOL rearrangement. This effect was found to be more pronounced with increasing W concentration in the supports. Regardless of the catalyst formulation used, increasing P_{H₂} resulted in lower hydrogenation activity. Conducting experiments with catalysts at various synthetic steps led to a comprehensive resolution of the reaction mechanism. A two-step metal induced hydrogenation of the intermediate, 4H2CP, was found to be the slowest step in the reaction network to obtain CPO. This bottleneck could only be overcome by slightly increasing Pt content in the catalyst, resulting in ~ 64 % CPO yield and high selectivity for sample with lowest W content. Long-term operation of the catalytic bed demonstrated stable activity for at least 38 h of continuous operation.

1. Introduction

Sustainable alternative chemicals derived from renewable sources such as lignocellulosic biomass will play a significant role as global chemical production grows. Furfural, derived from C5 fraction of lignocellulosic biomass, has been considered as an attractive platform molecule [1]. Hydrogenation of furfural can selectively yield furfuryl alcohol (FOL), which can be used as a foundry binder, resin [2] and flavoring agent [3]. FOL is, in itself, a valuable platform molecule with diverse applications. Its hydrogenation can yield tetrahydrofurfuryl alcohol (THFA) [4], 2-methylfuran [5,6] and cyclopentanone (CPO)

[7]. CPO has been used in synthesis of fragrances such as methyl dihydrojasmonate, cosmetics and household cleaning products [8,9]. In addition, it can be used as a precursor to synthesize bio-based (C10-C15) jet fuels by aldol condensation with furfural [7,10–13,14]. The growing importance of CPO as a solvent in the lithography manufacturing process has led to semiconductor factories to investigate its recycling and alternative sustainable production, thereby highlighting its importance in the modern high-tech era [15].

Therefore, the synthesis of CPO has become a prominent research focus, emphasizing enhancements in selectivity and catalyst stability. Previous reports have obtained a range of CPO yields (50–80 %) using

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Cu/ZrO₂ [16], CuNiZn [17] and Co-Ni bimetallic catalysts [18]. All these works performed the conversion in a batch configuration within 150–170°C and 30–80 bar H₂ pressure. Furfural has been predominantly used as a precursor for CPO synthesis. However, our previous study demonstrated that a selective single step conversion of furfural is rather difficult due to parallel ring hydrogenation pathways leading to THFA and 2-methyl tetrahydrofuran (2-MTHF) formation. Furthermore, the challenge lies in addressing catalyst stability and carbon loss issues from FOL hydrogenation, as 100 % FOL yields can be obtained from furfural hydrogenation at very mild conditions in aqueous phase. [19]. These previous observations, corroborated by Baldenhofer et al. [16], highlight the use of FOL as a suitable precursor for selective CPO production under aqueous phase conditions. Besides this, numerous works have clarified the role of solvents and catalytic supports in the multi-step FOL hydrogenation to CPO (see Fig. 1). Although the presence of water appears to be an essential factor in steering the conversion towards CPO, it simultaneously presents challenges concerning catalyst stability [20]. Irrespective of the catalyst used, the first step in the reaction network is the acid-catalyzed ring rearrangement of FOL to 4-hydroxy-2-cyclopentenone (4H2CP). This is followed by a simultaneous water elimination and hydrogenation to produce 2-cyclopentenone (CPEN) and subsequent hydrogenation to yield CPO. Several parallel reactions also occur from FOL: first, its hydrolysis to form levulinic acid (an important platform molecule); [1] second, the polymerization of FOL; and third, the furanic ring hydrogenation to form THFA. The challenge therefore lies in maximizing the initial selectivity towards FOL rearrangement to form 4H2CP, challenged by a high carbon loss attributed to FOL resinification and several aforementioned parallel reaction pathways. As shown by our previous work [19] and the works of Hronec et al. [21] and Yang et al., [22] low FOL concentration is preferred to reduce its

resinification. Moreover, it has been shown that minimal resinification occurs in steps beyond 4H2CP to CPO [22].

Our previous work [19] reinforced the importance of acidity (precisely, its strength) in driving selectively toward FOL rearrangement to 4H2CP, where ZrO₂ was used as the support. Numerous works on aqueous and organic phase processing have used Ti [23], W [24], Se [25] or Nb [26,27] based mixed oxides with Zr as catalytic supports, as they exhibit high hydro-thermal stability. Combining WO_x and ZrO₂ in different molar ratios could present a modulation of Brønsted and Lewis acid-base characteristics, [24,28] crucial for the selective multi-step transformation of FOL to CPO. A hydrogenating metal in conjunction with the supports is required for the reduction steps. Various works have used non-noble metals such as Cu [19,29], Ni [30] and Co [31] for FF hydrogenation to CPO. These metals exhibit a marked tendency to leach under aqueous phase conditions [32–34] and corroborated by our previous work [19]. Therefore, using noble metals such as Pt [35], Pd [21], Au [36], Ru [37], resistant towards leaching, for aqueous phase hydrogenation reactions is preferred. Moreover, noble metal hydrogenation has consistently proven to work under less severe operating conditions as opposed to non-noble metals.

In light of the above, this work used a mixed metal oxide of W and Zr as the support for dispersion of Pt as an unexplored catalytic combination to study FOL hydrogenation to CPO under aqueous phase conditions using a continuous flow reactor. This study demonstrates the advantages of these highly stable and tunable catalytic materials for the selective conversion of FOL to CPO. Further, new insights into the reaction mechanism by linking their performance with the physicochemical properties at different molar ratios of W and Zr in the support in their oxidized and reduced state were found. Pt loading and hydrogen pressure were varied to study their influence on hydrogenation of the

Fig. 1. Summary diagram of the multi-step reaction including the current investigated FOL to CPO hydrogenation process.

intermediates formed from 4H2CP. This work culminates with a long-term stability test of the best performing catalyst, resolving the stability challenges involved in aqueous phase processing such as relevant carbon losses, CPO yields and catalyst leaching, up to a period of 38 h of time on stream.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Catalyst synthesis

The W-Zr mixed oxide supports were prepared by micellant-assisted method found elsewhere [38]. For this purpose, 5 g of hexadecyltrimethylammonium bromide (CTAB; Sigma-Aldrich; CAS no.: 57-09-0; $\geq 97\%$ purity) was added to 100 mL of distilled water in a round-bottom flask heated to 70°C in an oil bath. Three different molar ratios of W and Zr were prepared for this study, respectively (W:Zr = 3:7, 5:5, 7:3). Herein, two different solutions of the metallic precursors, ammonium metatungstate hydrate (Thermo Fisher Scientific; CAS no.: 12028-48-7; 98% purity) and zirconium nitrate (Carl Roth GmbH; CAS no.: 13986-27-1, $\geq 98\%$ purity) were prepared by dissolving the pre-requisite amount in 10 mL of distilled water. These precursor solutions were then added drop-wise to the CTAB solution followed by addition of 20 mL of 28 wt% NH₄OH solution (Thermo Fisher Scientific; CAS no.: 1336-21-6) to obtain a precipitate. The solution was maintained at 70°C for 24 h under reflux and then transferred to an autoclave for aging at 100°C for 24 h. The solution was vacuum filtered and the solid obtained was dried at 100°C followed by calcination at 550°C for 6 h at 2°C min⁻¹. The supports obtained by this methodology are named in this work as: W_{0.3}Zr_{0.7}-C, W_{0.5}Zr_{0.5}-C and W_{0.7}Zr_{0.3}-C.

A portion of the above-mentioned supports underwent heat-reductive treatment (explained below). These reduced supports were denoted by W_xZr_y-R. The remaining calcined support powder was added with 1 or 3 wt% Pt by incipient wetness-impregnation using Pt(NH₃)₄(NO₃)₂ (Thermo Fisher Scientific; CAS no.: 20634-12-2; 99.99% purity) as precursor and methanol as solvent. This was followed by calcination at 550°C for 6 h at 2°C min⁻¹. The obtained catalysts were named as (1 or 3)% Pt/W_xZr_y-C (where, x and y refers to the molar ratios of W and Zr of the support, and C refers to the calcined catalysts). Further reduction with 10% H₂ / 90% N₂ at 550°C for 5 h at 2°C min⁻¹ was performed. The reduced samples were named as (1 or 3)% Pt/W_xZr_y-R.

2.2. Catalysts characterization

The textural analysis of the specimens under study was conducted by low temperature (88 K) N₂-physisorption using AUTOSORB iQ-C-MP-AG-AG (Quantacrome Instruments, USA). The specific surface area was determined by Brunauer-Emmet-Teller (BET) equation [39], while the total pore volume (V_{tot}) was obtained at the relative pressure P/P₀ = 0.99 using BJH method [40]. The same method was applied for the calculation of the average pore diameter (D_{pores}) and pore size distribution.

X-ray powder diffraction patterns were obtained by a Rigaku Mini-Flex 600 diffractometer with Cu-K α (0.154 nm) source and equipped with a K β (x2) filter with constant step of 0.02°2 θ and counting time of 2 s per step. Intensity at angles between 10–70° was measured at a rate of 0.6° min⁻¹. SmartLab Studio II and ICDD-PDF4 + (2023) database were used for phase composition identification. Unit cell parameters and mean crystallite sizes were determined by Rietveld refinement using Profex 5.2.

Thermogravimetric analysis in temperature programmed reduction (TPR-TGA) were conducted in a Netzsch STA 449-F5 “Jupiter” thermos-microbalance. For this purpose, 50 mg of sample were pre-treated in an inert atmosphere (N₂; pure N60; flow 50 mL min⁻¹) in an isotherm of

200°C for 40 min, to eliminate moisture or organic contaminants. Subsequently, 50 mL min⁻¹ of H₂ (5% in Ar) was flushed during a programmed temperature ramp rate of 2°C min⁻¹ up to 550°C. Once the temperature reached 550°C, the thermogravimetric analysis continued at the same temperature and reductant flow parameters for 4 h. Mass loss as a function of time is obtained directly from the equipment.

UV-vis measurements were done on a Jasco V-650 UV-vis spectrophotometer, equipped with an accessory for diffuse reflectance spectroscopy for powder samples, with a 1 cm diameter quartz window. All oxidized and reduced samples analyzed in this study were crushed in an agate mortar and dehydrated. The Kubelka-Munk function (F(R_∞)), for infinitely thick samples, was used to convert reflectance measurements (R_{sample}) into equivalent absorption spectra using the reflectance of BaSO₄ as reference (R_{BaSO₄}) as per the formula below:

$$R_{\infty} = \frac{R_{\text{sample}}}{R_{\text{BaSO}_4}}$$

$$F(R_{\infty}) = \frac{(1 - R_{\infty})}{2R_{\infty}} = \frac{\alpha(\text{absorption coefficient})}{S(\text{scattering coefficient})}$$

Ex-situ X-Ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) was carried out on a Thermo Scientific K-Alpha spectrometer. A few milligrams of powdered sample were deposited on a double-sided carbon tape and then transferred into the analysis chamber at room temperature. The chamber was evacuated to achieve ultra-vacuum conditions (2·10⁻⁸ mbar). Spectra were collected using monochromatic Al K α X-rays at 1486.6 eV running at 72 W and a spot size of 400 μ m. Spectra were acquired using a flood-gun source to account for surface charging. Survey and high-resolution scans for W, Zr, O, Pt were performed for all the samples. The pass energy of the survey and high-resolution scans were set at 50 eV for W, Zr and O (20 scans were collected) while for Pt were used 10 eV (50 scans). The data was analyzed using the software CasaXPS. Before analysis of the data, the binding energy data was referenced to the C 1 s line (285 eV) for charge correction. The curve fitting procedure and all the parameters used for them (line shapes, FWHM ratios and position constraints) were taken from the work of Moulder et al [41] and Sharpe et al [42]. The processing of the measured spectra includes a subtraction of Shirley-type background [43]. The peak positions and areas are evaluated by a symmetrical Gaussian-Lorentzian (30 and 60% Lorentzian contribution) curve fitting. The relative concentrations of the different chemical species are determined based on normalization of the peak areas to their photo-ionization cross-sections, calculated by Scofield [44]. The multiplet splittings and area ratios were constrained according to the parameters indexed Moulder et al. of the core level related to the species. The absolute binding energy values and FWHM were allowed to vary by

± 0.1 – 0.2 eV respectively to allow a better self-adjustment for error associated with charge referencing to adventitious C 1 s

NH₃-temperature programmed desorption (TPD) measurements were performed in AutoChem II 2920 equipped with a thermal conductivity detector. For a typical measurement, the samples were first degassed at 200°C with He, followed by NH₃ adsorption (2% in He) at 90°C. He was flowed over the catalytic bed to remove physisorbed NH₃ followed by temperature ramp of 2°C min⁻¹ from 100 to 700°C in presence of He.

Transmission electron microscopy (TEM), was performed by means of JEOL JEM 2100 high resolution transmission electron microscope at accelerating voltage of 200 kV. All samples were finely dispersed in an ethanol / water = 2 solution, dropped onto Cu TEM grids, and dried before the measurements. Selected area electron diffraction (SAED) mode was applied for diffraction patterns accumulation and HR-TEM imaging was used for lattice fringes registration.

CO₂ chemisorption was performed using Micromeritics 3Flex apparatus. Samples were heated at 2°C min⁻¹ to 300°C and held for 4 h in order

to remove adsorbed CO₂ and H₂O. After cooling the samples to 40°C, evacuation was performed. Then, CO₂ adsorption isotherm was obtained between 2.7 and 53 kPa. The linear low-pressure part of the isotherm was extrapolated to zero for calculating CO₂ chemisorption uptakes.

2.3. Catalytic activity testing and analysis of the liquid products

Catalytic activity testing was performed in flow experiments using a stainless steel reactor (inner diameter = 1 cm and length = 10 cm). For a typical experiment, 0.2 gram of the catalyst was diluted with 3.8 g of 400 mesh silicon carbide (SiC; Sigma Aldrich; CAS no.: 409-21-2; ≥ 97.5 % purity) and packed between quartz wool and glass beads on either side. The reactor was used in upflow configuration yielding an optimum catalyst wetting [45]. Liquid reactant was pumped using ISCO pump and hydrogen flow rate was controlled using a mass flow controller (MFC). The reactor pressure was controlled using a Bronckhorst back pressure controller. Samples were taken at different intervals in a gas-liquid separator to ensure steady state operation of the catalytic packing. The flow conditions used in this work are 0.2 mL min⁻¹ of 1 wt % FOL (Sigma Aldrich; CAS no.: 98-00-0; 98 % purity) in water and 4 NmL min⁻¹ of H₂ flow, resulting in a WHSV of 0.6 g_{FOL} g_{cat}⁻¹ hr⁻¹, if mentioned otherwise. It should be noted that the total pressure of the reactor was maintained in excess of the vapor pressure of both water and FOL (i.e., 8 and 1 bar at 170°C, respectively). Hence, the reaction occurs only in the liquid and solid catalyst phase. The liquid samples obtained were filtered through a polyvinylidene fluoride (PVDF) syringe filter to remove solids. The samples were then analyzed via Shimadzu GC-2010 Plus gas chromatograph using CPSIL5CB capillary column (30 m by 0.25 mm with 1 μm packing). Product yields, conversion and carbon loss are expressed in subsection 2.1 of SI.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Catalyst characterization

3.1.1. X-ray powder diffraction (XRD)

X-ray powder diffraction (XRD) was used to identify and clarify the evolution of the crystallographic phases along the entire synthesis process. As shown in Fig. 2-A, the degree of crystallinity in the catalytic supports calcined at 550°C increases as Zr concentration decreases, shifting from an amorphous W_{0.3}Zr_{0.7}-C to a crystalline W_{0.7}Zr_{0.3}-C mainly consisting of monoclinic WO₃ phase (PDF 96-152-8916). It should be noted that characteristic reflections of ZrO₂ were absent in all

the calcined supports. Subjecting the supports to impregnation with 1 wt % Pt and subsequent calcination, presented two reflections located at 2θ = 39.7° and 46.4° (planes (111) and (200), respectively: PDF 96-101-1104), as shown in Fig. 2-B. The exclusive presence of these two additional reflections suggests that the annealing temperature used is sufficient to form Pt⁰ crystallites from Pt(NH₃)₄(NO₃)₂ precursor. The self-reduction mechanism of Pt species in a static oxygenated environment has been already demonstrated by Falco et al [46], where the stabilization of metallic Pt nanoparticles on mixed W-Zr oxides at high temperatures (≥400°C) is especially favored using ammoniated precursors as compared to its chloridic counterpart. The diffractograms of reduced W-Zr supports, shown in Figure S1, still exhibit a low long-range ordered array for W_{0.3}Zr_{0.7}-R and W_{0.5}Zr_{0.5}-R supports. In case of W_{0.7}Zr_{0.3}-R sample, it is evident how the reductive process converted the monoclinic WO₃ phase into a distorted assay, cautiously attributed to a mix of cubic H_x-WO₃ and monoclinic WO_{3-x} (PDF 46-1096 and PDF 96-154-8687, respectively).

The manifestation of a reductive process undergoing multiple phase transitions is evidenced by the significant diversification of crystallographic phases observed in the reduced Pt-containing catalysts shown in

Fig. 3. XRD patterns of Pt impregnated reduced catalysts. Markers indicate the as-obtained XRD patterns.

Fig. 2. XRD patterns of W-Zr mixed metal oxides (A) and Platinum doped supports (B) after calcination referred to the monoclinic WO₃ and cubic Pt⁰ simulated patterns.

Fig. 3. 1 % Pt/W_{0.3}Zr_{0.7}-R sample, in addition to an extensive amorphous component shows the existence of tetragonal ZrO₂ phase with reflections positioned at $2\theta = 30^\circ, 35^\circ$ and 50.8° (PDF 96–230–0613), consistently with high concentration of Zr. In all samples, no reflections of monoclinic WO₃ were detected.

The prominent appearance of reflections centered at $2\theta = 35.3^\circ, 39.7^\circ$ and 43.6° , were identified as metallic W (PDF 96–900–8584), with the crystallite size proportionally dependent on W concentration in the catalyst. Similar behaviour was seen in case of Pt⁰ crystallite size, increasing from 18.6 to 44.6 nm with higher W content as depicted in Table S1. The presence of intermediate phases of WO_x with increasing crystallinity as the concentration of tungsten in the samples increases, suggests a gradual mechanism of reduction of WO₃ which transiently adsorbs hydrogen, converting W⁶⁺ into W⁰ in a multi-step mechanism. Evidence of this hypothesis can be proved by the presence in the two catalysts, 1 % Pt/W_{0.5}Zr_{0.5}-R and 1 % Pt/W_{0.7}Zr_{0.3}-R, of the cubic lattice of the H_x–WO₃ (Hydrogen-tungsten bronze, PDF: 46–1096) and of the monoclinic tungsten dioxide (WO₂ PDF 96–154–8687). The particular “asymmetrical shoulder” shown by the peak centered at $2\theta = 39.7^\circ$ in the sample with the highest W concentration, suggests the presence of another crystalline phase, having a cubic lattice with compressed cell parameter compared to that of W⁰ ($a = 5.0830 \text{ \AA}$). The Rietveld refinement has in fact found positive results in the addition to the model of the inter-metallic compound W_{0.66}Zr_{0.33} having a cubic lattice (lattice parameters $a = 3.1720 \text{ \AA}$; PDF: 96–152–7157) with a higher intensity peak centered at $2\theta = 40.2^\circ$ related to the (110) plane.

3.1.2. Temperature programmed reduction - thermogravimetric analysis (TPR-TGA)

The TPR-TGA comparative study of the catalysts, shown in Fig. 4, allows rationalization of the aforementioned multi-step reduction mechanism. The mixed W-Zr supports and a reference WO₃ (commercially obtained) show an onset of mass loss at relatively low temperatures (about 180°C), could be attributed to the reduction of the most defective components within the W-Zr oxide mixture. The sample with the highest W content, W_{0.7}Zr_{0.3}-C, also showed a propaedeutic increase in mass from ~260°C, followed by mass loss above 300°C. The reason for this initial mass growth could be ascribed to the formation of tungsten bronze, i.e., H_x–WO₃ (Figure S1), an intercalation product of WO₃ already reported in other works, to form at ~250°C [47]. The synthesis of this bronze can thus be considered pivotal for continuation of the reduction process, forming WO_{3-x} species possibly terminating with formation of W⁰ as shown in other works [48].

The stabilization of this intercalation compound is, in fact, closely dependent on the size of WO₃ crystallites (referred to as “tungstate domains”) for W-Zr mixed oxides, as shown by Barton et al. [47] Surface

sites with a density lower than 4 W nm^{-2} , appear to be incapable of stabilizing tungsten bronze and therefore unable to proceed with further reductions. Hence, the process of H₂ intercalation and reduction is nearly absent in the isothermal portion of TPR-TGA for W_{0.3}Zr_{0.7}-C but reaches the highest rate with increased W content in W_{0.7}Zr_{0.3}-C sample. These observations are consistent with the XRD analysis (Figure S1). Therefore, since the reduction process in these samples is constrained only by large tungstate domains (some of which are unevenly present in W_{0.3}Zr_{0.7}-C as well), the reduction proceeds slowly, “normalizing” the weight loss of samples to around 2 wt% over the course of the entire H₂ pre-treatment.

Fig. 4-B shows similar changes in the reductive process, for supports impregnated with 1 % Pt. As demonstrated earlier, W-Zr supports subjected to Pt impregnation and subsequent calcination result in formation of Pt⁰ crystallites (see Fig. 2-B). Without excluding the possible reduction of a fraction of platinum oxide (not yet reduced during the synthesis process or due to passivation), the trend of the reduction curves for 1 % Pt/W_{0.5}Zr_{0.5}-C and 1 % Pt/W_{0.7}Zr_{0.3}-C samples still appear to indicate a mass loss mechanism. However, as the temperature rises, starting from 360°C, an additional contribution to Pt⁰-induced reduction of WO_x becomes evident. In comparison with the bare supports, Pt impregnated catalysts display a clear increase in the mass loss rate with a slow but continuous reduction that remains incomplete during the five hours of isothermal treatment. The XRD pattern seen in Fig. 3 is thus the result of the high H₂-chemisorption and spill-over abilities of Pt⁰ crystallites [49, 50]. The presence of the latter, therefore enhances the reduction and dehydroxylation processes of the supports, modifying the electronic and surface structure of W and Zr species as a function of WO_x domain sizes.

3.1.3. Transmission electron microscopy (TEM)

Figure S3, S4, Figs. 5 and 6 show TEM micrographs of 1 % Pt/W_{0.3}Zr_{0.7} and 1 % Pt/W_{0.7}Zr_{0.3} catalysts after calcination and reduction processes, respectively. Consistent with previous findings, Figure S3 confirms the presence of Pt⁰ nanoparticles for 1 % Pt/W_{0.3}Zr_{0.7}-C, as described by XRD analysis (Fig. 2-B).

In 1 % Pt/W_{0.7}Zr_{0.3}-C (Figure S4), the electron diffraction of the sample area solely shows the presence of monoclinic WO₃ crystallographic planes. From the high-resolution micrograph of the same sample (Figure S4-B), it is possible to visualize an isolated PtO₂ particle of about 10 nm, which is plausibly derived from an incomplete self-reduction of the ammoniated precursor or a further passivation process of metallic Pt. As observed by correlating the XRD patterns and TPR-TGA curves, the effects of reductive processes on the crystallographic structure, even in the presence of Pt, are relatively moderate for 1 % Pt/W_{0.3}Zr_{0.7}-R. The metal nanoparticles visible in Fig. 5 by electronic transparency on an amorphous support, could be identified as Pt⁰.

Fig. 4. TPR-TGA reduction profiles of the W-Zr supports (A) and Pt impregnated (B) catalysts.

Fig. 5. TEM micrographs of the sample 1 % Pt/W_{0.3}Zr_{0.7}-R. (A) 40k magnification. (B) 100k magnification. (C) 600k magnification.

Fig. 6. TEM micrographs of the sample 1 % Pt/W_{0.7}Zr_{0.3}-R. (A) 40k magnification. (B) 100k magnification. (C) 300k magnification.

1 % Pt/W_{0.7}Zr_{0.3}-R (Fig. 6) shows a clear separation of the metallic component (probably W⁰) from the bulk cluster of the support, due to sintering processes of W moieties into large particles. Analysis of the spacing of a region of interest of the aggregate in Fig. 6-B, shows in high resolution the crystallographic planes of monoclinic WO₂ and those of cubic W⁰ (Fig. 6-C). These reduction products were found in larger crystallite sizes compared to its W_{0.3}Zr_{0.7} counterpart (see Table S1).

3.1.4. N₂ physisorption and textural characterization

N₂-physisorption was used to investigate the change in textural properties (listed in Table 1) as a function of the thermal processes undergone during the synthesis procedure. Adsorption-desorption isotherms of mixed W-Zr oxides are shown in Figure S5. The micellant-assisted synthesis increases the exposed surface area (S_{BET}) of the mixed metal oxides, compared to their commercial WO₃ and ZrO₂ counterparts. As W concentration increases, there is a noticeable decrease in the specific surface area (S_{BET}) from 189.8 to 45.6 m² g⁻¹ for W_{0.3}Zr_{0.7}-C and W_{0.7}Zr_{0.3}-C, respectively.

A general trend of decreasing mesoporous volume with W content can be observed with bare and reduced supports. Modifying these materials with Pt precursor results in pore reorganization. Pore size distributions (Figure S6) demonstrate that increasing Zr content not only enhances surface area values (S_{BET}), but also, with the subsequent heat treatment steps, helps in the constraining of a more uniform and decreased size of the pores. A more detailed discussion on the hysteresis loop can be found in SI.

3.1.5. X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS)

X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) was performed to characterize the chemical state and relative abundance of elements on the

Table 1

Textural properties of the samples under investigation compared with commercial ZrO₂ and WO₃ and temperature programmed desorption of NH₃ normalized by S_{BET} .

Sample	S_{BET}^a (m ² g ⁻¹)	V_{total}^b (cm ³ g ⁻¹)	D_{pores}^b (nm)	NH ₃ Uptake	
				(mmol g ⁻¹)	(μ mol m ⁻² g ⁻¹)
ZrO ₂	61.8	0.31	10.7	–	–
WO ₃	5	0.03	2	–	–
W _{0.3} Zr _{0.7} -C	189.8	0.23	3.7	0.459	2.42
W _{0.5} Zr _{0.5} -C	73.5	0.15	3.7	0.295	4.01
W _{0.7} Zr _{0.3} -C	45.6	0.10	3.5	0.214	4.69
W _{0.3} Zr _{0.7} -R	178.4	0.22	3.7	0.252	1.41
W _{0.5} Zr _{0.5} -R	69.6	0.15	3.7	0.151	2.17
W _{0.7} Zr _{0.3} -R	37.9	0.09	3.9	0.077	2.03
1 % Pt/W _{0.3} Zr _{0.7} -C	145.3	0.20	3.5	–	–
1 % Pt/W _{0.5} Zr _{0.5} -C	61.7	0.17	6.2	–	–
1 % Pt/W _{0.7} Zr _{0.3} -C	65.5	0.15	3.5	–	–
1 % Pt/W _{0.3} Zr _{0.7} -R	160.4	0.13	3.7	0.499	3.11
1 % Pt/W _{0.5} Zr _{0.5} -R	68.4	0.09	3.3	0.324	5.25
1 % Pt/W _{0.7} Zr _{0.3} -R	59.6	0.16	3.5	0.202	3.39

^a - Specific surface areas calculated from the BET equation,

^b - Mesopore volumes obtained from the BJH desorption calculation method.

surface of the catalysts, shown in Table S2. The examination of W 4f core levels of W_xZr_y-C and W_xZr_y-R supports are shown in Figure S7. The spectra of calcined samples displays a relative abundance mostly originating from W⁶⁺, with photoelectron emission from the 4f_{7/2} orbitals at binding energy (BE) of 35.9 eV, and from the relative spin-orbit coupling (4f_{5/2}) positioned $\Delta E=2.18$ eV. At low BEs around 30.7 eV, a doublet with an area ratio of 1:2, intensity proportional to Zr content of the samples, can be observed. The increased binding energy of about 1.8 eV of Zr⁴⁺ 4p signals suggests a strong interaction between W and Zr core levels. Similar XPS spectra was observed for reduced supports (Figure S7-B), with an additional presence of reductive intermediates of WO₃. With increasing W content, in fact, WO_{3-x} species can cautiously be identified in the region between 32 and 35 eV. At the highest binding energies according to Yue et al., oxidation states of W⁵⁺ and W⁴⁺ can be ascribed (at about 34.5 and 33.5 ± 0.2 eV, respectively) [51]. Binding energies between 33.5 and 31.5 ± 0.2 eV, on the other hand, can be attributed to lower W oxidation states between W⁴⁺ and W⁰ [52,53]. A careful analysis of the spectra in the region around 31.3 eV evidences the contribution of W⁰ besides the existence of Zr⁴⁺ 4p core level, as confirmed by the work of Vaidyanathan et al. [54]

As shown in Fig. 7, impregnation with Pt and calcination brings no particular change in W 4f core level emission. The Pt 4f region, on the contrary, is the most complex to resolve, owing to a low Pt concentration in the sample (i.e., 1 %) combined with its close proximity to W core level 5s. Consistent with XRD and HR-TEM results (Fig. 2 and Figure S3), the annealing procedure of the $\text{Pt}(\text{NH}_3)_4(\text{NO}_3)_2$ precursor generates Pt^0 crystallites evidenced by the emission of photoelectrons at $\text{BE} = 71.3 \text{ eV}$ from core level 4f_{7/2}. With a relative abundance proportional to Zr content in the samples, at a binding energy of around 72.8 eV the presence of an oxidized Pt component usually associated with the presence of Pt^{2+} is revealed [55]. No signals from Pt^{4+} were detected (at higher $\text{BE} = 74.9 \text{ eV}$), but their presence, due to passivation upon exposure to atmosphere, cannot be excluded. It is evident that increase of W in the samples favors stabilization of Pt^0 species.

The XPS spectra of the $\text{Pt}/\text{W}_x\text{Zr}_{1-x}\text{-R}$ samples in Fig. 8 show the changes brought by the reductive process on the surface of the catalysts. The changes observed in the W 4f core level region indicate a notable increase in the proportion of reduced tungsten oxides (WO_{3-x}), as evidenced by contributions with BEs ranging from 34.7 eV to 35.2 eV (seen in the $\text{Pt}/\text{W}_{0.7}\text{Zr}_{0.3}\text{-R}$ sample). Samples with higher W content exhibit a distinct photoemission profile at low BE region of 31.2 eV originating from W^0 species, distinguishable from Zr 4p orbitals.

Similar to its unreduced counterparts, an increase in Pt^0 content with W loading was observed (see Table S2). The XPS analysis therefore allows us to confirm two hypotheses already carved out from the XRD (Fig. 3) and TPR-TGA (Fig. 4) analyses: I) The presence of Pt^0 crystallites strongly increases the extensive multi-step $\text{WO}_3 \rightarrow \text{H}_x - \text{WO}_3 \rightarrow \text{WO}_{3-x} \rightarrow \text{WO}_2 \rightarrow \text{W}^0$ reductive process; II) The molar ratios of ZrO_2 present in the mixed metal oxides acts as a “modulating agent” in the reductive process of the Pt and W species.

3.1.6. Diffuse reflectance ultraviolet-visible and Raman spectroscopy

Key information about the electronic structure at domain size of W-Zr mixed oxides and determination of their local molecular surface

Fig. 8. XPS spectra of the W 4f and Pt 4f core levels of 1 % $\text{Pt}/\text{W}_x\text{Zr}_{1-x}\text{-R}$ catalysts.

structures can be gained by diffuse reflectance UV-vis in conjunction with Raman spectroscopy. As discussed in more detail in subsection 1.5 of SI, the WO_3 absorption edge is strictly induced by indirect transitions due to overlapping d orbitals in the W-O-W bonds. The energy of the absorption edge is therefore closely related to the degree of disorder introduced in what can be defined as a quasi-infinite domain of WO_x polyhedra. Figure S8, shows the DR-UV-vis spectra of the $\text{W}_x\text{Zr}_{1-x}\text{-C}$ samples, indicating increase in the degree of disorder of the WO_x domains induced by the progressive increase in ZrO_2 concentration. In support of this thesis, analysis of the Raman spectra of the $\text{W}_x\text{Zr}_{1-x}\text{-C}$ supports (Fig. 9-A) was conducted. The vibrational peaks, located at 807, 712, 326, 270 cm^{-1} correspond to symmetrical and asymmetrical stretching, bending and rotational vibrations of W-O-W bonds, respectively. The latter are particularly intense for $\text{W}_{0.7}\text{Zr}_{0.3}\text{-C}$ sample, and decrease as the degree of disorder induced by the W-O-Zr bonds increases. The size of WO_3 domains obtained through a combination of SEM-EDX (Figure S9) and S_{BET} (Table 1) for different W-Zr supports, places these materials in three distinct surface W density ranges: $\text{W}_{0.7}\text{Zr}_{0.3}$ equal to 11.7 W nm^{-2} , $\text{W}_{0.5}\text{Zr}_{0.5}$ equal to 6.4 W nm^{-2} and $\text{W}_{0.3}\text{Zr}_{0.7}$ equal to 1.5 W nm^{-2} . The calculated values of surface densities of tungstate domains were found to be in line with the three macro categories reported by Barton et al. [47] and Ross-Medgaarden et al. [56] for similar catalysts, i.e.: materials with WO_3 surface densities $< 4 \text{ W nm}^{-2}$, $4 < \text{W nm}^{-2} < 8$ and above 8 W nm^{-2} . As highlighted in Barton's research, the three surface conditions of the tungsten domains are crucial not only for the Brønsted acid properties of the materials, but also for their reductive behavior (as described previously in TPR-TGA), which in turn significantly impacts their catalytic performance. As already mentioned, hydrogen at low temperatures can intercalate within the crystalline lattice of monoclinic WO_3 , forming $\text{H}_x - \text{WO}_3$. In addition to being the major bottleneck for further reductive processes between tungsten oxide species, according to Barton et al. it also represents the major promoter in the genesis of Brønsted acid sites within neutral WO_x structures [47].

Fig. 7. XPS spectra of the W 4f and Pt 4f core levels of the 1 % $\text{Pt}/\text{W}_x\text{Zr}_{1-x}\text{-C}$ catalysts.

Fig. 9. Raman spectra of the W_xZr_y -C supports (A) and reduced Pt containing catalysts (B).

The formed amount of these acid species on the surface and in the bulk of the larger WO_x domains is reflected in the color variation of W-Zr mixed oxides after the hydrogen treatment. The transition from yellow-green, in case of $W_{0.7}Zr_{0.3}$ -C, to blue color after reduction can be explained by a substantial lowering of the absorption edges and provide a qualitative hint towards the extent of formation of Brønsted acid sites. The color change is due to the insertion of electrons of the hydrogen atoms within the LUMO orbitals of the WO_3 , which at this point can be excited to the unoccupied states available, at moderately higher energies [47]. The stabilization of the Brønsted acid sites, and thus the formation of $H_x - WO_3$, depends on the concentration and size of WO_3 domains in the samples. This is reflected in increase of absorption energy, between 1.8 and 2.2 eV, with increasing W content for bare supports (shown in Fig. 10). Additionally, the partial preservation of absorption spectra for $W_{0.3}Zr_{0.7}$ -R from its unreduced precursor confirms this inability of small sized WO_x domains in stabilizing $H_x - WO_3$.

In W_xZr_y -R samples, there is a downshift in characteristic WO_3 vibrational modes to lower energies, reflecting the weakened W-O-W bonds, and the structural changes induced by hydrogen intercalation and the formation of oxygen vacancies (Figure S10). Partial reduction of WO_3 to WO_2 , is reflected in the Raman spectra for W domain size (6.5 W nm^{-2}) in the $W_{0.5}Zr_{0.5}$ -R sample. This reduction leads to the emergence of a peak at 788 cm^{-1} , which may indicate structural modifications or intermediate phases, and an enhancement of the band at 931 cm^{-1} associated with the stretching mode of the sites $W=O$ [57]. A combination of these reductive processes has been observed in the $W_{0.7}Zr_{0.3}$ -R sample, which, due to the larger WO_3 domain size

(11.5 W nm^{-2}), as previously described, exhibits a more extensive reductive process.

The Pt/ W_xZr_y -R samples and their reduced parents exhibit spectra (shown in Fig. 9-B) that show a flattening of the Raman active modes previously described, probably due to coverage-dampening effect of the surface Pt nanoparticles [58]. In addition, in Fig. 9-B, it can be observed that the Pt impregnation and calcination procedure, in the Pt/ $W_{0.3}Zr_{0.7}$ -C sample, reveals the Raman vibrations of Zr-O-Zr bonds corresponding to a tetragonal zirconia phase, with peaks located at 200, 324, 368, 464, and 610 cm^{-1} . This sample's surface catalytic properties seem to be predominantly influenced by the active sites of zirconia, in stark contrast to the Pt/ $W_{0.7}Zr_{0.3}$ -R sample. In the latter, even after the reductive process, tungstate domains remain evident, as indicated by the characteristic W-O-W stretching vibrations. This suggests that while the Pt/ $W_{0.3}Zr_{0.7}$ -R sample is primarily governed by zirconia's acidic or basic active sites, the Pt/ $W_{0.7}Zr_{0.3}$ -R sample retains significant contributions from W-O bonds, pointing to a different catalytic behavior rooted in the preserved tungstate domains.

3.1.7. Ammonia temperature programmed desorption (NH_3 -TPD) and CO_2 chemisorption

Ammonia temperature programmed desorption (NH_3 -TPD) was used to characterize the amount and strength of acid active sites on the surface of samples. The desorption profiles presented in Figure S11 can be divided into three distinct temperature regions: 100–250, 250–400 and 400–600°C. These ranges correspond to an increasing strength of acidic sites with increasing desorption temperatures. In the NH_3 -TPD profiles

Fig. 10. Diffuse Reflectance UV-Vis of reduced bare supports and color variation after the reduction of the bare calcined supports.

shown in Figure S11-A, the temperature range of 100–250°C is typically associated with weak acid sites, which can originate from partially coordinated cations (weak Lewis acid sites) or surface hydroxyl groups (weak Brønsted acid sites). Notably, within this range, there is a clear trend of increasing relative concentration of weak acid sites as Zr content increases. This corresponds with a relative reduction in the size of WO_3 domains, indicating that higher Zr loading promotes a greater density of weaker acid sites. The attribution of these weak acid active sites predominantly to hydroxyl groups is mirrored by the fact that in the catalytic supports, after the reductive process in Figure S11-A, a strong decrease in weak acidity is evident in all samples due to the dehydroxylation phenomenon previously described in Fig. 4-A. Another feature which disappears after the reductive process are the two peaks present in the temperature range between 500 and 650°C of the $\text{W}_{0.7}\text{Zr}_{0.3}\text{-C}$ support. The latter are generally associated with strong acid sites which, given the nature of the catalyst, belong to WO_3 crystallites which, after the reductive treatment, give place to the already described reduced W phases that are free of this type of acidity. From a quantitative point of view, the normalized values of NH_3 adsorbed per exposed surface area of the samples and thus of Lewis-Brønsted acid sites, shown in Table 1, appear to follow a linear upward trend as W content increases.

This trend is maintained, albeit at approximately half the concentration due to dehydroxylation, even in the reduced catalytic supports. However, as shown in Figure S11-B and Table 1, in 1 % Pt/ $\text{W}_x\text{Zr}_y\text{-R}$ catalysts, the addition of Pt increases the total content of adsorbed NH_3 , particularly in the temperature region attributed to weak acid sites. This effect is most pronounced in the Pt/ $\text{W}_{0.5}\text{Zr}_{0.5}\text{-R}$ sample, which features an intermediate concentration of Zr and WO_3 domain size. This increase can be attributed to the high dispersion and partial passivation of Pt nanoparticles in these samples, which may enhance the overall surface acidity by interacting with both the support and adsorbed ammonia.

The basic properties of the tungsten-zirconia supports, measured via CO_2 chemisorption (Figure S12), increase with higher Zr content. This is due to ZrO_2 being more basic and sensitive to CO_2 adsorption compared to WO_3 [59]. In samples containing a higher concentration of Zr, the material exhibits dual functionality, providing both acidic and basic active sites. On the other hand, the $\text{W}_{0.7}\text{Zr}_{0.3}$ -based catalysts, due to their higher W concentration, do not appear to exhibit any basic sites. Furthermore, even though the normalized acidity may seem comparable to other catalysts, the low exposed surface area and the large size of the tungsten domains significantly reduce the number of exposed acidic active sites and thus their catalytic accessibility and effectiveness in case of $\text{W}_{0.7}\text{Zr}_{0.3}$ based catalysts.

3.2. Catalytic activity testing

3.2.1. Catalytic performance

Figs. 11, 12 and S13 present the catalytic performance for aqueous phase FOL hydrogenation of all synthetic phases of the catalysts, at 150 and 170°C and 32 bar H_2 pressure. Regardless of the W_xZr_y molar ratios for the bare and reduced supports, conversion of FOL between 60 % and 85 %, with high selectivity for 4H2CP, was observed. 4H2CP yields remained between 50 % and 65 %. This selectivity is attributed to the initial protonation and rearrangement of FOL. Only trace amounts of subsequent hydrogenated products were detected using the supports only (Fig. 1). Less than 5 % CPEN yields were obtained and a complete absence of its hydrogenated derivatives, CPO and CPL was observed. Doping the bare supports with 1 % Pt followed by calcination resulted in CPEN and CPO detection in the product stream. This can be attributed to the presence of Pt^0 crystallites (confirmed using XRD and XPS, see Fig. 2 and 7, respectively). FOL was reduced to CPEN with yields between 15 % and 30 % for all Pt/ $\text{W}_x\text{Zr}_y\text{-C}$ catalysts, while CPO yields remained below 6 %. Finally, reducing the Pt/ W_xZr_y catalysts, revealed ≥ 90 % FOL conversion, but at the operating conditions in question (150°C and 32 bar H_2 pressure), it demonstrated an evident difficulty in satisfactorily reducing 4H2CP. The highest observed CPO yield was ~ 10 % using

Fig. 11. Product distribution for $\text{W}_{0.3}\text{Zr}_{0.7}$ based catalysts for 150°C (top panel) and 170°C (bottom panel). Reaction conditions: $C_{\text{FOL}} = 1$ wt% in water, $Q_{\text{feed}} = 0.2$ mL min^{-1} , $Q_{\text{H}_2} = 4$ NmL min^{-1} , $W_{\text{cat}} = 0.2$ g, $W_{\text{SIC}} = 3.8$ g, $\text{WHSV} = 0.6$ $\text{g}_{\text{FOL}} \text{g}_{\text{cat}}^{-1} \text{hr}^{-1}$.

Fig. 12. Product distribution for $\text{W}_{0.7}\text{Zr}_{0.3}$ based catalysts for 150°C (top panel) and 170°C (bottom panel). Reaction conditions: $C_{\text{FOL}} = 1$ wt% in water, $Q_{\text{feed}} = 0.2$ mL min^{-1} , $Q_{\text{H}_2} = 4$ NmL min^{-1} , $W_{\text{cat}} = 0.2$ g, $W_{\text{SIC}} = 3.8$ g, $\text{WHSV} = 0.6$ $\text{g}_{\text{FOL}} \text{g}_{\text{cat}}^{-1} \text{hr}^{-1}$.

1 % Pt/ $\text{W}_{0.3}\text{Zr}_{0.7}\text{-R}$ catalyst. Other byproducts originating from the furanic ring hydrogenation of FOL such as THFA, MTHF were not detected in the GC analysis. However, noticeable loss of carbon

(approximately in the range of 20–30 % mole basis, as shown by other works [16,60]) was visually detected by the presence of oligomeric species, further confirmed by GC-MS in the form of dimer and trimers of FOL, as shown in our previous work [19].

Although not particularly high performing, the tests conducted using calcined and reduced forms of the supports and Pt-doped catalysts at 150°C still present useful information for understanding the catalytic process. Regardless of the presence of reduced W phases ranging from WO_2 to W^0 for $W_{0.7}Zr_{0.3}$ -R, the reduction of 4H2CP seems to be unfeasible. Hydrogenation of 4H2CP is perceptible only after the addition of an exclusive hydrogenating metal such as Pt. The non-linear trend of the conversions also suggests that the simultaneous dehydration and hydrogenation of 4H2CP to form CPEN may be potentially affected at operating conditions by a thermodynamic barrier that is difficult to rationalize without additional speculations.

The tests conducted at 170°C and 32 bar H_2 pressure, reported in Figs. 11, 12 and S13 (bottom panel), show how the increased temperature contributes to > 90 % FOL conversion for all catalysts explored. The enhanced protic properties of the solvent (i.e., water at 170°C) in combination with the solid acid catalysts significantly increase the protonation of FOL to 4H2CP. In bare supports, this results in 4H2CP yields close to or exceeding 70 %, with further increase up to 80 % with the reduced supports $W_{0.3}Zr_{0.7}$ -R and $W_{0.5}Zr_{0.5}$ -R. Although traces from reductive processes (CPEN) were detected with the bare oxidized and reduced catalyst supports, the increased temperature does not enhance the hydrogenation activity of Pt/ $W_{0.7}Zr_{0.3}$ -C, which produces CPEN and CPO with yields lower than 10 %. In contrast, Pt/ $W_{0.3}Zr_{0.7}$ -C and Pt/ $W_{0.5}Zr_{0.5}$ -C show an increase in CPO production, reaching yields of approximately 20 %. Consistently, Pt/ W_xZr_y -R catalysts were the best performing, reducing approximately 50 % of the 4H2CP to CPEN, followed by further reduction to yield CPO. This was particularly notable for the Pt/ $W_{0.5}Zr_{0.5}$ -R catalyst, which achieved yields of 30 % and 25 % for CPEN and CPO, respectively. Although evident that temperature plays a pivotal role in the hydrogenation of intermediates, it does not completely resolve the sequential reduction of 4H2CP, progressing through CPEN and selectively arriving at CPO. In fact, although the observed improvements have progressively shown the evolution of this multi-step reductive process, a good selectivity CPO was not achieved yet, using 1 wt% Pt. Improvement in the hydrogenation performance of the catalysts, however, was achieved by increasing the Pt content to 3 wt %, leading to a non-trivial result.

The tests carried out with the supports impregnated and reduced with 3 % of Pt are indicated by the far-right bars in the activity results. At 170°C, 3 % Pt/ $W_{0.5}Zr_{0.5}$ -R and 3 % Pt/ $W_{0.7}Zr_{0.3}$ -R converted more than 90 % of FOL, producing 40 % and 50 % CPO yields, respectively, adjoined by an incomplete conversion of CPEN (~ 15 %), with negligible amounts of 4H2CP in the product stream. The 3 % Pt/ $W_{0.3}Zr_{0.7}$ -R catalyst exhibited superior catalytic activity among all the catalysts tested, achieving a yield of ~ 64 % CPO, with a comparable percentage of FOL conversion to its counterparts. Milder reaction conditions can be used with 3 % Pt/ $W_{0.3}Zr_{0.7}$ -R, i.e., 32 bar H_2 and 170°C as compared to 38 bar H_2 and 180°C, while using Cu-based catalysts as shown in our previous work (64 % vs. 61 %, respectively)[19]. Despite the enhanced hydrogenation capacity of the 3 % Pt/ W_xZr_y -R catalysts at 150°C, evident through increased relative CPO selectivity (determined by the ratio of $CPO / (\sum 4H2CP + CPEN + CPO)$), low W content catalysts showed a drop in feed conversion at this temperature. Increased temperature and Pt loading exert an evident beneficial effect on the hydrogenation performance of the catalysts. Greater H_2 pressures might yet result in better hydrogenation activity.

Increasing H_2 pressures from 32 to 44 bar instead manifested an unexpected yet noticeable deceleration of hydrogenation activity on all 1 % Pt/ W_xZr_y -R catalysts irrespective of temperature, as shown in Figure S15. FOL conversion decreases with W content in the catalyst (Figure S15-A), while the hydrogenation products (especially CPO), always exhibit lower yields at higher H_2 pressures. Although increased

temperature contributes, as already proven, to an increase in FOL conversion as well as to an increase in the reductive properties of the three catalysts, tests conducted at 160°C (Figure S15-B) and 170°C (Figure S15-C) continue to have evident decreases in the hydrogenation rates depending on the hydrogen pressure used during the activity tests. This phenomenon could be assigned to the increased solubility of hydrogen in the aqueous medium at higher pressures, resulting in competitive adsorption (i.e., poisoning or blocking) upon the active sites for hydrogenation of intermediates, namely 4H2CP and CPEN, hindering the catalytic activity.

3.2.2. Mechanistic considerations

Earlier experiments demonstrate a pivotal dependence of temperature on both FOL conversion and hydrogenation activity of the catalysts. Understanding the individual steps in the multi-step mechanism of FOL hydrogenation is crucial to explain this effect. In this section, we elaborate on the origin of catalytic activity for respective intermediate conversion steps. The first step to selectively obtain CPO is the protonation and related rearrangement of FOL into 4H2CP. This path (shown in Fig. 13) begins with the formation of the oxonium cation on FOL molecule to form molecule (A). Subsequent elimination of water with formation of the transition intermediate (B) occurs. Eventually, 4-hydroxy-2-cyclopentenone (4H2CP) is formed through a rearrangement by eliminating the oxygen atom from the heterocycle, through a 4 π -conrotatory cyclization. The formation of 4H2CP is then followed by reductive and dehydration steps, in unbeknownst sequence, leading to 2-cyclopentenone (CPEN) formation. Further reduction of its C=C bond, leads to the formation of cyclopentanone (CPO), the carbonyl group can eventually be further reduced to an alcohol group forming cyclopentanol (CPL). It should be noted that two competitive reaction pathways from FOL exist in addition to the Piancatelli rearrangement. First pathway is the removal of water from FOL to yield 2-methyl furan (2-MF), while the second is furanic ring hydrogenation of FOL to yield THFA. Moreover, subsequent hydrogenation of 2-MF and THFA lead to formation of 2-methyltetrahydrofuran (2-MTHF) and pentanediols, respectively. All the aforementioned products were not detected in this work.

The Piancatelli mechanism suggests that hydronium H_3O^+ ions originating from aqueous media due to higher reaction temperatures, i.e., $\geq 150^\circ C$, could catalyze FOL rearrangement to 4H2CP (Fig. 13). To confirm this hypothesis, blank tests with SiC as reactor packing were performed at 150–170°C (Table S4). Substantial conversion of FOL to 4H2CP was observed already at 150°C and liquid residence time of 3.1 min. Prolonging the residence time to 7.5 min results in an almost complete FOL conversion and 57 % 4H2CP selectivity. Increasing temperature to 170°C, further boosts 4H2CP selectivity to 72 % and complete FOL conversion. All the tests performed with solid acid catalysts used the same liquid residence time, i.e., 3.1 min. Consequently, the protonation of FOL is primarily facilitated through homogeneous catalysis (H_3O^+ from water at elevated temperatures), with additional assistance from acid sites located within the heterogeneous solid catalysts (see Table 1 for NH_3 -TPD results). The nonlinear trend of FOL conversion in the experiments shown in Figs. 11, 12 and S13 at 150°C therefore results from a combinatorial situation in which the different ratios of W_xZr_y -C interact with FOL by stabilizing or not the intermediates generated in the rearrangement shown in Fig. 13. It is worth noting, the blank test and all molar ratios of platinum-free supports, revealed no consistent traces of products derived from an actual hydrogenating process, i.e., THFA, CPEN, CPO and/or CPL, as gaseous H_2 was also used in the feed.

The contribution of Pt therefore as a hydrogenating agent is quite evident from the calcined catalysts with low metal content, but especially in the reduced catalytic versions 3 % Pt/ W_xZr_y -R. The data obtained from the catalytic experiments suggest that the CPEN product only starts to be found in relevant quantities after the addition of Pt, which suggests that to hydrogenate the 4H2CP molecule, the presence of

Fig. 13. Furfuryl alcohol reduction mechanism, focused in the protonation of FOL to 4H2CP as suggested by Piancatelli et al.[61].

H_2 chemisorption and spill-over mechanism is essential. Such hydrogenated product distribution following 4H2CP highlights a more than legitimate doubt regarding how its reduction to CPEN occurs mechanistically; since the overall reaction is a combination of water elimination (dehydration) and a reduction of the unsaturated ring, still unbeknownst in its sequence. This doubt is reinforced by the fact that even 1 % Pt/ W_xZr_y -R catalysts at 170°C, although having a reducing contribution from W^0 , exhibits molar yield ratio (Y_{CPO}/Y_{CPEN}) less than unity, an outcome that can only be counteracted at this operating temperature by adding 3 wt% Pt. Interestingly, addition of Pt to the catalyst does not lead to preferential hydrogenation of FOL to form either THFA, 2-MF or 2-MTHF, suggesting that the Piancatelli rearrangement (i.e., combination of homogeneous and heterogeneous catalysis) is a favourable pathway within the conditions explored despite the high H_2 pressures (32 and 44 bar).

An explanatory hint for such catalytic behavior in the mechanistic network could be found through a metal-induced double-step

hydrogenation process, suggested in Fig. 14. In fact, since the direct elimination of the hydroxyl group of 4H2CP is unlikely due to the formation of anti-aromatic compound (namely, cyclopenta-2,4-dien-1-one), it could be assumed that 4H2CP incurs an initial hydrogenation of the double bond operated by the Pt^0 particle. Furthermore, this unsaturated bond being conjugated to the carbonyl group and thus electron-poor increases the likelihood of a preferential hydrogenation of this 4H2CP moiety. This hypothesis is bolstered by negligible change in 4H2CP yield while using $W_{0.7}Zr_{0.3}$ -R or other bare supports possessing acid sites on the surface at 170°C, confirming the necessity of 4H2CP conversion to proceed via hydrogenation as the first step. Once what can be nomenclatured as 2-hydroxycyclopentanone (2HCPO) is formed, the Brønsted acid sites present on the catalysts as well as the aqueous environment and high temperatures can favor the rapid protonation of the hydroxyl group and subsequent elimination of the water leaving group, thus forming CPEN. The latter which will be secondarily hydrogenated to CPO, predominantly by Pt^0 . Due to the relative abundance of

Fig. 14. Mechanism suggested to describe a double-step metal-induced hydrogenation in the conversion of 4H2CP to CPEN followed by CPO.

CPEN and no 4H2CP in the liquid product obtained from reaction at 170°C for 1 % Pt/W_{0.3}Zr_{0.7}-R, the hydrogenation of CPEN can thus be considered the slowest step to obtain CPO because of insufficient metal induced hydrogenation rate due to low Pt⁰ loadings. Increasing Pt loadings to 3 wt% enables sufficient hydrogenation activity to reduce CPEN content in the product and maximizing CPO yields. The contribution of W⁰ species, while modest, in supplementing hydrogen chemisorption ability cannot be excluded and warrants future investigation.

The selectivity towards CPO is related to the amount of Pt⁰ together with the presence of acid-base sites in the supports originating from the different molar ratio of W-Zr mixed oxides in the catalysts. A general trend of increasing selectivity towards CPO with the Zr content of the samples was observed. As extensively described, the samples of the W_{0.3}Zr_{0.7} series in fact feature a high surface area (Table 1), WO₃ domains in the range below 4 W nm⁻² that best expose the Brønsted acidity peculiar to WO₃ (Table 1 and S3), but also a contribution of basic sites inherent to ZrO₂ (Figure S12). The latter could be useful as anchoring and directing agents for protonation and hydrogenation reactions of 2HCPO (undetected in GC-MS) on the surface of the catalysts. XPS, TEM, Raman and DR-UVvis analysis of the W_{0.3}Zr_{0.7}-derived samples in fact show that WO_x are highly dispersed in a solid solution with ZrO₂ (Figs. 8, 5, 9 and 10). The support portions proximal to the Pt particles therefore present all the acid-base and hydrogenating sites required for selective reduction of 4H2CP. Similar hypothesis of W and active metal species in close proximity can induce enhanced product yield was proved by Zhang et al. [62] Lower 4H2CP and consequent higher CPEN and CPO yields while using Pt/W_{0.3}Zr_{0.7}-R (as shown in Fig. 11) highlight these key findings. It has also been shown by XRD (Fig. 3), XPS (Fig. 8) and TPR-TGA (Fig. 4) that even in the presence of Pt⁰, the lack of stabilization of H_x - WO₃ in these samples prevents the extensive reduction of WO₃ domains and thus the partial elimination of Brønsted acid sites, as occurs in samples with a higher W concentration. This reductive process, moderated by Zr in 1 % Pt/W_{0.3}Zr_{0.7}-R and 3 % Pt/W_{0.3}Zr_{0.7}-R catalysts, not only preserves the support's characteristics but also stabilizes Pt⁰ particles with an average crystallite size of 19–20 nm, irrespective of Pt loadings, leading to minimal presence of CPEN in the liquid product due to a higher hydrogenation activity attributed to smaller crystallite size (see Table S1). Conversely, in samples reduced with a higher concentration of W, the reductive process leads to the sintering of Pt crystallites, with an average size exceeding 40 nm at both Pt loadings. This also results in the formation of WO₂ or metallic W crystallites, which exhibit low or negligible acidity. On the other hand, WO₂ species may catalyze oxidative reactions through tungsten radical mechanism as shown by Li et al. [63] Additionally, an extensive formation of WO₂, induced by Pt, is particularly visible in the X-ray diffraction pattern of the 3 % Pt/W_{0.7}Zr_{0.3}-R sample (see Figure S2), corroborating these suggestions. The presence of such reduced W species with unexposed ZrO₂ moieties lead to a lower CPO yields (< 50 %) with an incomplete reduction of CPEN (~ 20 % yield) as detected in the liquid product.

3.2.3. Long-term stability testing

Previous observations show that carbon loss mainly occurs in the initial polymerization step, hindering maximum CPO yield. The formation of these oligomeric species can lead to coke/carbon deposition on the catalyst surface, potentially blocking active sites and causing deactivation. The formation of oligomeric species is enhanced at higher FOL concentrations as shown by several works [16,19,60] due to second-order dependence of polymerization kinetics on FOL. Furthermore, as shown in Table S4 and according to Baldenhofer et al. [16], the oligomerization is primarily driven by the nature of the solvent (i.e., water) and affected by feed concentration, and not severely determined by the catalyst used; therefore, the loss of carbon cannot be eluded, lowering the CPO yield (mole basis). The catalytic bed packed with 3 % Pt/W_{0.3}Zr_{0.7}-R was subjected to 30 h of continuous exposure (intermittent operation with overnight standby) to 1 wt% aqueous FOL solution

at its optimal reaction conditions for maximum CPO yield. It should be noted that prior to this test, the same catalytic bed was used for another 8 h campaign, where FOL hydrogenation was conducted at 32 bar H₂ pressure and 150–170°C. In between these tests, the bed was left unwashed. Fig. 15 shows relatively constant performance (particularly the CPO yield) along the time-on-stream. The total ketonic yield obtained from rearrangement of FOL (i.e., sum of 4H2CP, CPEN and CPO) also remains constant. Thus, although 30 % of FOL presumably leads to polymeric species, no significant deactivation is observed, suggesting that these species are not strongly bound to the catalyst. Previous reports corroborate this hypothesis that the oligomers are predominantly in the range of 200–250 g mol⁻¹, are possibly water soluble, [16] and can be removed after washing of the catalyst bed with water. Incidental variations in product distributions in Fig. 15 arise from subtleties in the experimental procedure. First, the initial sample after restarting the experiment shows the lowest CPO yields due to the induction time required to re-establish steady state operation. Besides, the first 8 h segment shows relatively lower CPO yield, and correspondingly higher CPEN and 4H2CP than the remaining segments. This is attributed to the unwashed species present in the bed at the beginning of the operation. Thus, the catalyst bed was washed with distilled water (flushing with a flow rate of 1 mL min⁻¹) after the first 8 h segment, and the same procedure was repeated every time the operation was temporarily interrupted. After resuming tests on the following day, recovery of the catalytic activity was observed, as seen from the results between 25 and 35 and 55–70 h. Hence, replenishment of the catalytic bed with aqueous feed is necessary to maintain long-term stability for at least 38 h of operation. Inductively-coupled Plasma (ICP) investigation did not show any W or Pt leaching in the aqueous phase.

Due to the multi-site and multi-step conversion of the reaction intermediates, quantification of turn over frequency (TOF) is not plausible. On the other hand, the occurrence of H_x - WO₃ species (H₂ chemisorption ability of the support) hamper an accurate determination of Pt⁰ sites and therefore, the estimation of a site-time-yield. Hence, a space-time-yield including the mass of catalyst was calculated [64]. In addition to the activity stability of 3 wt% Pt/W_{0.3}Zr_{0.7}-R over a period of 38 h, a CPO productivity, i.e., space-time-yield (STY), of 0.33 g_{CPO} g_{cat}⁻¹ hr⁻¹ was achieved. Table 2 shows the productivities achieved with different catalysts at various reaction conditions. All the listed works were conducted using a batch reactor configuration whereas this work was performed using continuous flow configuration. It should be noted that while our work uses a diluted feed (1 wt%), other works have used feed concentrations ranging from 2 to 5 wt%. Besides, irrespective of the active metal used for hydrogenation, STYs listed in Table 2 are of similar order of magnitudes.

Fig. 15. Catalyst long term stability test using 3 % Pt/W_{0.3}Zr_{0.7}-R. Reaction conditions: T = 170°C, P_{H₂} = 32 bar, W_{cat} = 0.2 gs, W_{SIC} = 3.8 g, C_{FOL} = 1 wt% in water, Q_{feed} = 0.2 mL min⁻¹, Q_{H₂} = 4 NmL min⁻¹, WHSV = 0.6 g_{FOL} g_{cat}⁻¹ hr⁻¹. NOTE: The grey region indicates aqueous feed and hydrogen flow being switched off and reactor cooled down to room temperature.

Table 2
Comparison of space-time-yields (STY) for CPO production from different catalysts.

Catalyst	Temperature (°C)	P _{H₂} (bar)	CPO yield (%)	STY (g _{CPO} g _{cat} ⁻¹ hr ⁻¹)	Reactor	References
3 wt% Pt/W _{0.3} Zr _{0.7}	170	32	64	0.33	Continuous flow	This work
Cu/ZrO ₂ ^a	160	80	20	0.87	Batch autoclave	[13]
10–10 wt% Co-Ni/TiO ₂	150	40	80	0.29	Batch autoclave	[31]
3 % Pt–3 % Co/Ca	180	10	70	0.45	Batch autoclave	[65]
10 % NiCu50/SBA–15 ^b	160	40	62	0.33	Batch autoclave	[22]
25 wt% Cu/ZnAl	160	40	62	0.21	Batch autoclave	[66]
2 wt% Ni/SiO ₂	160	30	83	0.24	Batch autoclave	[30]
CuNiAl ^a	140	40	95	0.34	Batch autoclave	[67]

^a - Active metal loading in wt% is unavailable,

^b - Ni and Cu are in equimolar ratio.

4. Conclusion

Mixed tungsten-zirconium oxides prepared by hydrothermal micellar-assisted method were found to be effective and durable catalytic supports for aqueous-phase hydrogenation of FOL to CPO. The variation of tungsten and zirconium molar ratios could tune the catalytic properties of these materials, especially after doping with platinum as a hydrogenating agent. Specifically, it was found via TPR-TGA, XRD, XPS, that in catalysts with a higher tungsten concentration, the size of the tungstate domains favors a vigorous reduction of the latter, with a consequent decrease in acidity, necessary for the reaction under study. The three molar ratios of zirconia-tungstates resulted in three different theoretical sizes of tungstate domains. Large tungstate domains led to reduction of WO_x to W⁰ and this effect was enhanced by presence of platinum during reductive treatment of the catalyst. Higher zirconium concentration inhibits the extinction of tungstate acidic domains and stabilizes smaller Pt⁰ crystallites and greater catalyst surface area. Moreover, it imparts a fraction of Brønsted-Lewis basic sites to the catalysts, which were found in reduced quantities or completely absent in the catalysts with a higher tungsten content.

For the conducted catalytic tests, FOL conversion and product yield were found to be optimal at 170°C and 32 bar H₂ pressure. In contrast, lower temperatures or higher H₂ pressures led to a decrease in catalytic outputs. The first step of the reaction, i.e., FOL rearrangement to 4H2CP, was found to be homogeneously catalyzed by water at high reaction temperatures. The platinum-free catalysts were found to synergistically contribute to FOL rearrangement along with water. Only an exclusive doping of the supports with platinum led to consecutive hydrogenation of 4H2CP to CPEN. Importantly, adjoining these results with undoped platinum supports reveal that the formation of CPEN from 4H2CP preferentially follows hydrogenation step of the C=C bond followed by a water elimination step, limiting the hydrogenation rate as a function of the platinum loading. Highly dispersed Pt⁰ crystallites and exposed ZrO₂ sites found in 3 % Pt/W_{0.3}Zr_{0.7}-R were the most active in catalyzing the hydrogenation of 4H2CP and CPEN to selectively form CPO (64 % yield). Using this catalyst formulation, stable CPO production could be achieved for at least 38 h of continuous operation. Further investigation with higher FOL concentrations in aqueous phase using a flow-through configuration is warranted to accelerate future CPO synthesis on a larger scale.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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Appendix A. Supporting information

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found in the online version at [doi:10.1016/j.apcatb.2025.125400](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apcatb.2025.125400).

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